

Managing Editor's Column

Vol. 2, No. 3; March 28, 1996

Dear Readers:

J.UCS Vol.2, No.3 is another typical issue in the sense that it contains a good mix of material, from the applied to the theoretical: I hope you will enjoy reading it.

Please note that the whole Vol.1 (1995) of J.UCS is available on CD-ROM from Springer. I also have still a number of copies left, so you can have one at no charge as long as supplies last by just dropping me a note: hmaurer@iicm.tu-graz.ac.at.

Note finally that our electronic library is now starting to grow beyond J.UCS. Check http://www.iicm.tu-graz.ac.at/electronic_library. It is going to be much polished and extended within the framework of the European project "LIBERATION". This acronym stands for LIBraries: Electronic Remote Access To Information Over Networks. I will let you know more about it as it progresses.

With best wishes,

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'H. Maurer', with a long horizontal flourish extending to the right.

Hermann Maurer
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